

Inverted papilloma: experience of a tertiary centre

André S. Machado, Ana Silva, Cecília Almeida e Sousa

Department of Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery, Centro Hospitalar
Univeristário do Por-to, Porto, Portugal

Email: sousamachado.andre@gmail.com

Abstract:

Inverted papillomas represent one of the most common benign neoplastic lesions located in the sinonasal tract. Owing to the local erosive behavior, tendency to recur and the potential for malignant transformation, surgical management of inverted papillomas is often challenging.

Objective: This study aimed to analyze the surgical outcomes of patients with inverted papillomas, according to the Krouse staging and the different surgical approaches. **Methods:** Retrospective study of patients diagnosed with sinonasal inverted papillomas who underwent surgical treatment between 2011 and 2016 at a tertiary referral hospital. Cases with follow-up less than 12 months were excluded. The rate and the time of recurrence were the main outcomes. Values of $p < 0.05$ were considered statistically significant.

Results: Twenty-two cases with mean age of 59,23 years, predominantly male (81.8%), were included.

Krouse T1 Stage corresponded to 54.5%; T2 occurred in 22.7% of cases; while T3 and T4 Stages accounted for 22.74% and 0% of patients, respectively. We documented a recurrence rate of 27.3%. All inverted papilloma relapses occurred up to 2 years post-operatively. No case of malignant transformation was recorded.

Keywords:

Inverted papilloma, nose, neoplasm, surgery

Biography:

Dr. André Machado is Master in Medicine from the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Beira Interior. Residency in Otorhinolaryngology and Cervical-Facial Surgery at Centro Hospitalar Universitário do Porto. Member of the Portuguese Society of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery. Member of the Spanish Society of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery. Member of the Medical Association. Invited Professor Curricular Units of Otorhinolaryngology and Laboratory of Practical Skills of the 5th year of the Integrated Master in Medicine at the Faculty of Health Sciences of the University of Beira Interior.. Former guest trainer in the Academia da Especialidade® courses to prepare students of the 6th year of medicine for the National Test of Access to Medical Internship.

ENT in primary health care - training and experience of Portuguese general practitioners

André Machado, Vitor Pais², Fábio Nunes³, Carlos Faria⁴, Ana Silva¹,
Cecília Almeida e Sousa¹

¹Department of Otolaryngology Head and Neck Surgery, Centro Hospitalar
Univeristário do Porto, Porto, Portugal,

²USF São Simão da Junqueira,

³USF Infante D. Henrique,

⁴USF Amare Saude

Email: sousamachado.andre@gmail.com

Abstract:

An open questionnaire was applied to doctors of general and family medicine in the north and center of Portugal in order to assess training levels and their experience in otorhinolaryngology (ENT). 105 responses were obtained. Most doctors of general and family medicine underwent an internship in ENT during the bachelor's / integrated master's degree (71.4%) - 97.3% of them considered the consultation as the greatest value in the same internship. 34.3% of respondents reported the frequency of sessions with a view to postgraduate teaching in ENT - mostly (58.3%) in the form of a lecture. 93.5% of respondents reported an interest in attending other ORL sessions. The estimate regarding the percentages of patients, both adult and pediatric, assessed during their clinical practice varies considerably. This study reflects the variability and the level of dissatisfaction in relation to ENT training by family doctors.

Keywords:

Otorhinolaryngology; Education, Medicine; Medical training; General and Family Medicine.

Biography:

Dr. André Machado is Master in Medicine from the Faculty of Medicine of the University of Beira Interior. Residency in Otorhinolaryngology and Cervical-Facial Surgery at Centro Hospitalar Universitário do Porto. Member of the Portuguese Society of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery. Member of the Spanish Society of Otorhinolaryngology and Head and Neck Surgery. Member of the Medical Association. Invited Professor Curricular Units of Otorhinolaryngology and Laboratory of Practical Skills of the 5th year of the Integrated Master in Medicine at the Faculty of Health Sciences of the University of Beira Interior.. Former guest trainer in the Academia da Especialidade® courses to prepare students of the 6th year of medicine for the National Test of Access to Medical Internship.

Subtotal Petrosectomy with Blind Sac Closure: Our Experience at a Tertiary Centre

Arjun gupta,¹ K C Prasad,¹ Kouser Mohammadi,¹ Abhilasha k,¹ Induvarsha,¹
Anjali PK,¹ Pratyusha K¹

Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck Surgery, Sri Devaraj Urs
Medical College, Kolar, Karnataka, India

Email: arjun8gupta@gmail.com

Abstract:

Subtotal petrosectomy with blind sac closure is an effective surgical procedure for diseases of the mastoid involving the middle ear, dura, carotid, inner ear and cerebrospinal fluid(CSF). This procedure aims at isolating the middle ear cleft from the external environment to eliminate the chances of intracranial spread of infection due to exposure of dura and inner ear fluids. In our study, 14 patients diagnosed with supralabyrinthine cholesteatoma with petrous apex involvement, meningoencephalocele, transverse fracture of the temporal bone with recurrent CSF otorrhea, spontaneous multiple CSF leaks, Glomus Jugulare & chronic otitis media with purulent labyrinthitis were included. Patients with parotid malignancy and tumors with intracranial extension were excluded from this study. The most commonest symptom being hearing loss and the most common intraoperative finding being exposure of inner ear fluids. Erosion of duramater and piamater makes this surgery more challenging. Obliteration of cavity with muscle flaps and fascia showed best results. All patients underwent the same procedure of subtotal petrosectomy with blind sac closure. We observed that there was no recurrence of disease in any of the cases after a mean follow up period of 1 year. The surgery is challenging and requires expertise for complete eradication of disease. Majority of complications are transient. Accurate imaging and meticulous surgery results in good outcome.

Keywords:

Subtotal petrosectomy, blind sac closure, csf otorrhea, meningoencephalocele, supralabyrinthine cholesteatoma, labyrinthitis

Biography:

Arjun Gupta is Resident in Department of Otorhinolaryngology and Head & Neck surgery Sri Devaraj Urs Medical College Kolar, Karnataka, India.

Adenoid Cystic Carcinoma of the Nasal Cavity: A Case Report

Dr. Chaitrashree. P

Post graduate Student, Mandya Institute of Medical Sciences, Mandya

Email: chaitrapn198@gmail.com

Abstract:

Introduction:

Sinonasal malignancy accounts for 1-2% of all head and neck malignancies. Adenoid cystic carcinoma is the 3rd most common of sinonasal malignancy. It is common in females compared to males at the ratio of 2:1 and the peak incidence at age of 5th to 6th decade of life. They are rarely seen in the nasal cavity where lateral nasal wall is the most common site. Its incidence in the nasal septum is 2.7% - 8.4% of sinonasal malignancy.

Case Report:

We report a case of 65 year old female patient who had history of right side nasal obstruction since 4 years which was insidious in onset, gradually progressive with recurrent bleeding from right nasal cavity since 3 months which was moderate in amount with 2-3 episodes per day. On anterior rhinoscopy, a fleshy mass was seen occupying the posterior part of right nasal cavity which was bleeding on touch. Diagnostic nasal endoscopy and CT PNS revealed a mass occupying the right nasal cavity arising from posterior part of septum extending into the nasopharynx. There were no neck nodes or distant metastasis. Biopsy of the mass showed features of Adenoid cystic carcinoma. She underwent endoscopic approach tumor resection followed by radiotherapy. The histopathological examination revealed features suggestive of Adenoid cystic carcinoma.

Conclusion:

Adenoid cystic carcinoma are slowly growing tumours which are amenable to surgical management. Many surgeons advocate local debulking surgery with adjunctive radiotherapy to improve patient's quality of life.

References:

1. Wardas P, Tymowski M et al. Endoscopic approach to the resection of adenoid cystic carcinoma of paranasal sinuses and nasal cavity. Eur J Med Res 2015;20,97.
2. Belaldavar BP, Batra R. Adenoid cystic carcinoma of the nasal septum. A rare case report. J Sci Soc 2013;40:39-40.

Biography:

Dr. Chaitra Shree. P, Completed her Post Graduation in the Department of ENT at Mandya Institute of Medical Sciences.

Reposition of Montelukast either alone or in combination with Levocetirizine against SARS-CoV-2

Dipankar Bhattachayya*, Ph.D.

Chichuria Institute of Medical Science & Research, India

Email: dipankarbhattacharya31@gmail.com

Abstract:

It has been hypothesised that antiallergic medications (AAMs) like montelukast and levocetirizine both the two bitter chloro compounds could be repurposed either alone or combinedly as an antiviral against SARS-CoV-2, like chloroquine/hydroxychloroquine (CQ/HCQ), another two bitter chloro compounds. Both AAMs and CQ/HCQ are bitter tasted chloro compounds. Depending on their these two similar physical properties and the safety and efficacy of AAMs by controlling over post viral episodes as comparing with viral inhibitory activities including SARS-CoV-2 by CQ/HCQ, a reposition of AAMs either alone/combinedly could be rationalised as an antiviral approach to nCoV.

References:

1. Present position and address: Principal Investigator, Chichuria Institute of Medical Science & Research, Thakurpara, Chichuria, Bethuadahari, Nadia, West Bengal, India-741 126
2. Former Senior Assistant Professor, PG Department of Biochemistry, Oriental Institute of Science and Technology, Rangamati, Midnapore(West), West Bengal, India-721 102
3. Former Post Doc Fellow, Center for Molecular Neurobiology, The Ohio State University, Columbus, USA, OH-43210
4. Former Ph.D. scholar and Research Associate, Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, 93/1-A. P. C. Road, Kolkata, West Bengal, India-700 009 + Jadavpur University, Kolkata, West Bengal, India-700 032
5. Former graduate student of Chemistry Honours from Ranaghat College and Post Graduate student of Biochemistry from Ballygunj Science College of Calcutta University, West Bengal, India

Preamble: Dr. Bhattacharyya has more than 28 years of research and 5 years of teaching experiences in different University and Institutes. Formerly he was a Protein Biochemist during his doctoral and postdoctoral study but presently doing research on repurpose of covid medicines. He has more than dozen of publication in reputed journals including patents and review. Also discovered and developed some specific natural medicines effective against asthma, gastritis and pain.

Extensive Mucormycosis of paranasal sinuses- A challenge to the surgeon

Kunal Thakur*, S.M Azeem Mohiyuddin

Sri Devaraj Urs University, Department of ENT & HNS, Kolar,
Karnataka, India

Email: kunal1291scorpio@gmail.com

Abstract:

Fungal Infections of nose and paranasal sinuses are frequently encountered in tropical and humid climates with Diabetic patients and immunocompromised individuals being predisposed to it. As the number of diabetic and immunocompromised patients is increasing the incidence of mucormycosis is also increasing. Mucormycosis is a rapidly spreading condition and involves the orbit and cranial cavity in a short duration of time thereby causing significant morbidity or mortality. The only drug active against this dangerous condition is Amphotericin B which has various adverse effects. Early surgical intervention involves aggressive debridement which can give rise to functional deficit and disfigurement. We have had a significant number of patients presenting with extensive mucormycosis of paranasal sinuses along with other co-morbidities. We intend to document the presentation of these cases, the predisposing conditions causing mucormycosis in this region and the outcome of treatment in our hospital. This study may help to sensitize the medical practitioners in our region regarding the possibility of this life threatening condition in immunocompromised patients as well as in patients with sinusitis not responding to treatment, thereby facilitating early diagnosis and appropriate treatment.

Keywords:

Mucormycosis, Amphotericin B

References:

1. Roden MM, Zaoutis TE, Buchanan WL, Knudsen TA, Sarkisova TA, Schaufele RL, Sein M, Sein T, Chiou CC, Chu JH, Kontoyiannis DP. Epidemiology and outcome of zygomycosis: a review of 929 reported cases. *Clinical Infectious Diseases*. 2005 Sep 1;41(5):634-53.
2. Spellberg B, Ibrahim AS. Recent advances in the treatment of mucormycosis. *Current infectious disease reports*. 2010 Nov 1;12(6):423-9.
3. Ambrosioni J, Bouchuiguir-Wafa K, Garbino J. Emerging invasive zygomycosis in a tertiary care center: epidemiology and associated risk factors. *International Journal of Infectious Diseases*. 2010 Sep 1;14:e100-3.

Choanal polyps: our experience in a tertiary care centre

Lini Joseph*, K.C Prasad

Sri Devaraj Urs Academy of Higher Education and Research,
Department of Otorhinolaryngology, Karnataka, India

Email: linijomedico@gmail.com

Abstract:

Choanal polyps are benign soft tissue lesions arising from nasal or paranasal sinus mucosa that extends through the choana into the nasopharynx. 1 Choanal polyps represent approximately 4-6% of all nasal polyps. 2 Patients with choanal polyp often presents with unilateral or bilateral nasal obstruction, snoring, nasal discharge, headache and epistaxis. Though Antrochoanal polyps i.e polyps arising from the maxillary sinus and extending to choana are more common, polyps arising from sphenoid sinus ostium, posterior part of middle turbinate, posterior nasal septum and posterior most part of inferior and middle meatus are quite uncommon. In our institution, we have encountered such polyps originating in these unusual areas and were missed on anterior rhinoscopy but could be visualized on posterior rhinoscopy and the site of origin was confirmed by a detailed Diagnostic nasal endoscopic examination. (Figure 1) In this retrospective study conducted at our centre, 14 patients with age ranging from 16-75 years who were diagnosed to have choanal polyps between 2016-2019 were enrolled. The presenting symptoms, past history, clinical examination details, nasal endoscopy findings and radiological details of these patients were retrospectively reviewed. Anterior rhinoscopic examination was unremarkable in all the cases. On posterior rhinoscopy, a polypoidal mass could be visualized in the nasopharynx in most of the patients (n=12) and a bulky mass could be directly visualized in the oral cavity in one patient. In this study, we aim to trace the site of choanal polyps originating from less common sites and to describe the clinical, radiological, histopathological characteristics, diagnostic challenges and their management.

Keywords:

Choanal polyp, septochoanal, sphenchoanal, polyp, Diagnostic nasal endoscopy

Figure 1: Thick stalk of septochoanal polyp extending through the choana into the nasopharynx

References:

1. Perić A, Vukadinović T, Kujundžić T, Labus M, Stoiljkov M, Đurđević BV. Choanal polyps in children and adults: 10-year experience from a tertiary care hospital. *European Archives of OtoRhinoLaryngology*. 2018
2. Segal N, Gluk O, Puterman M. Nasal polyps in the pediatric population. *B-ENT*. 2012; 8(4):265–267

Biography:

Dr. Lini Joseph has completed her MBBS at the age of 25 years from Dr. MGR educational and research institute University and currently doing her post-graduation in ENT in Sri Devaraj Urs Medical College, Karnataka. She has published a case report in *International Journal of Otorhinolaryngology and head and neck surgery* in Feb 2020 and is an aspiring researcher.

Anterior canal BPPV

Dr. Neha Shrivastava

Director, American Institute Of Balance & Consultant Neurotologist
And Ent Specialist, Rtkl Vertigo & Ent Clinic, India

Email: drnehashrivastava@yahoo.in

Abstract:

BPPV BENIGN PAROXYSMAL POSTIONAL VERTIGO is the most commonest form of vertigo. POSTERIOR canal though most commonly affected semicircular canal in Inner ear followed by Lateral semicircular canal; the topic of Anterior canal BPPV still remains a debatable and controversial topic. Vertical downbeat nystagmus still poses a challenge to all the Neurotologist and ENT Specialist all over the world and There are many differential diagnosis of the same.this topic will helps us simplify case and lead to clinical diagnosis of the condition.We have DR NEHA SHRIVASTAVA one of the youngest consultant Neurotologist and ENT specialist from Mumbai,India to guide us through this topic.

Biography:

Dr. Neha Shrivastava has finished her graduation of MBBS from Terna medical college and hospital, Nerul. She has completed her post-graduation in MS in Ear nose and Throat and head and neck surgery from PADMASHREE - DR DY PATIL medical college and hospital, Nerul. She carries a special interest in Neurotology and has her own vertigo and ENT clinic.

Basics in clinical diagnosis of vertigo

Dr. Neha Shrivastava

Director, American Institute Of Balance & Consultant Neurotologist
And Ent Specialist, Rtkl Vertigo & Ent Clinic, India

Email: drnehashrivastava@yahoo.in

Abstract:

Vertigo is a subjective symptom. It still remains a challenge to the ENT Specialist and general physician in current scenario to diagnose and treat a case of Vertigo. There are many differential diagnosis of vertigo. This topic helps us simplify case of vertigo and also lead to its diagnosis. We have DR NEHA SHRIVASTAVA one of the youngest consultant Neurotologist and ENT specialist from Mumbai, India to guide us through this topic.

Biography:

Dr. Neha Shrivastava has finished her graduation of MBBS from Terna medical college and hospital, Nerul. She has completed her post-graduation in MS in Ear nose and Throat and head and neck surgery from PADMASHREE - DR DY PATIL medical college and hospital, Nerul. She carries a special interest in Neurotology and has her own vertigo and ENT clinic

Head and Neck Oncology: Early Glottic Cancer

¹Dr Sarita Pandey Bhattarai, ²Prof J Fagan

¹MBChB (WSU – SA) FCORL (CMSA – SA), Consultant ENT, Head and neck surgeon Frere Hospital, East London, South Africa)

²Otorhinolaryngology, Division of Head and neck oncology, UCT Groote Schuur hospital, Cape town South Africa.

Email: saritajie@gmail.com

Abstract:

By definition, Early Glottic cancers are considered T1 and T2 lesions of the Glottis. Squamous cell Carcinoma is the most common type of Glottic tumour. These tumours tend to arise commonly in the anterior portion of the glottis and usually on the free margin of vocal cord. They tend to spread horizontally along the cord margin towards the anterior commissure. Glottic cancers are confined within the larynx for relatively long period. Due to the anatomical location and the restrictions by the laryngeal framework, they tend to present with symptoms early on.

Until late 1800s laryngeal cancer was considered a fatal disease that was palliated by tracheostomy and rarely cured by laryngofissure. Early experiences with laryngectomies were associated with mortality rates as high as 95%, but by 1900s improved patient selection and modification of techniques resulted in mortality rate of 8.5%. at the same time long term survival rates of glottic cancer rose from 4% to 44%.

During 20th century Total laryngectomy had been accepted as a standard of treatment for CA larynx while radiation therapy was recognised as an alternative for certain types and certain stages of the disease.

This talk aims to address the current treatment scenarios available for the Early Glottic tumours, while looking at the potential outcomes and the potential pitfalls in developing world scenario.

I will also introduce the management algorithm tool that Prof Fagan and his team of Head and neck surgeons have developed for the developing world. This takes into consideration all the factors that play a role in patient management.

Keyword:

Glottic cancer, Head and neck oncology, Laryngeal cancers, Total laryngectomy, Modified neck dissection, radiotherapy, adjuvant chemotherapy.

References:

Cummings Otolaryngology – 6th edition, Elsevier

<http://www.entdev.uct.ac.za/guides/open-access-atlas-of-otolaryngology-head-neck-operative-surgery>

<https://developingworldheadandneckcancerguidelines.com/>

Biography:

ENT Surgeon with passion for head and neck oncology surgical techniques. Demonstrated history of working in the hospital & health care industry. Skilled in Otolaryngology, Emergency Medicine, Healthcare Management, Healthcare, Clinical Research, and Strategic Planning. Strong healthcare services professional with a Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (M.B.B.S.) and a fellow of college of medicine (South Africa) Otorhinolaryngology division.

Paediatric Laryngology: Laryngeal cleft, Case report and discussion

¹Dr Sarita Pandey Bhattarai, ²Dr C Favara

¹MBChB (WSU – SA) FCORL (CMSA – SA), Consultant ENT, Head and neck surgeon Frere Hospital, East London, South Africa)

²ENT surgeon, Frere Hospital, East London South Africa

Email: saritajie@gmail.com

Abstract:

Laryngeal cleft is a rare congenital disorder of larynx. It is an abnormal closure of the trachea- oesophageal septum which results in a fistula/opening into the oesophagus, through which the baby aspirates. The degree of clinical symptoms vary from a mild stridor and aspiration of breastmilk noted as a coincidental finding postpartum. The degree of severity of Presenting symptoms is dependent on the degree of the cleft. Grade 1 and 2 will present with mild stridor with aspiration while grade 3 or 4 will present with massive aspiration and respiratory distress.

Diagnosis with this condition requires a unusually high degree of suspicion as well as a critical and accurate interpretation of investigation. Although we have dearth of investigations available, the gold standard of investigation in such cases is a thorough endoscopic evaluation.

In this presentation, we report and discuss a case of laryngeal cleft diagnosed and managed in Frere Hospital East London, South Africa. We describe our key route to diagnosis and detail surgical management plan for this case. (Figure 1)

A short discussion of the topic follows for academia.

Keyword:

Congenital malformation of larynx, paediatric airway pathology, laryngology, laryngeal cleft, flexible endoscopy as diagnostic tool for laryngeal cleft, tracheostomy, GORD in neonates. Reflux in neonates.

References:

1. Cummings Otolaryngology – 6th edition, Elsevier
2. Type 1 Laryngeal Cleft
3. A Multidimensional Management Algorithm: Shilpa Ojha, MBChB, MRCS1; Jean E. Ashland, PhD, CCC-SLP2,3; Cheryl Hersh, MA, CCC-SLP4,5; et al 2014
4. The Presentation and Management of Laryngeal Cleft A 10-Year Experience Reza Rahbar, DMD, MD Etal. Jama otolaryngology – head & neck surgery 2006

Biography:

ENT Surgeon with passion for head and neck oncology surgical techniques. Demonstrated history of working in the hospital & health care industry. Skilled in Otolaryngology, Emergency Medicine, Healthcare Management, Healthcare, Clinical Research, and Strategic Planning. Strong healthcare services professional with a Bachelor of Medicine, Bachelor of Surgery (M.B.B.S.) and a fellow of college of medicine (South Africa) Otorhinolaryngology division.

Tip test-a novel technique for understanding the cellularity of temporal bone.

Dr. Vyshnavi.V, Dr. K. C. Prasad

Sri Devaraj Urs Medical College, Tamaka, Kolar, Karnataka, India

Email: vyshnavi.vasudev@gmail.com

Abstract:

Introduction: In adults, the mastoid may be fully pneumatized, diploic (partially pneumatized), or sclerotic (non-pneumatized). The pneumatization may extend till the mastoid tip, squamous part of temporal bone, adjacent zygoma and occipital bone. However, the non-pneumatized mastoid bone may be made of solid bone/contain spongy diploic spaces filled with fatty marrow.^{1, 2} The cellularity of temporal bone determines the ease at which the surgeon can perform surgeries. We are introducing a simple tip test to characterize the pneumatization pattern of mastoid before performing the surgery.

Objective: To predict the cellularity of the temporal bone before addressing the mastoid by a tip test.

Materials And Methods: Prospective observational review of 126 temporal bones was done to determine the cellularity of the temporal bone before performing mastoid surgeries by a simple KCP's Tip test i.e, by drilling 1 or 2 strokes over the mastoid tip area for less than 5-7sec.

Results: Out of 126 temporal bones dissected, in 69.04% bones there was cellular mastoid and in 30.95% bones there was diploic/sclerotic pattern of pneumatization. In all the bones which were analysed, tip test was proved.

Conclusion: KCP's tip test is an innovative test to predict the pneumatization pattern of the mastoid intraoperatively before addressing the mastoid proper.

Keyword:

Dissection, KCP's (Dr.K.C.Prasad) tip test, mastoid tip, pneumatization

References:

1. Glasscock Shambaugh. Surgery of the Ear. In: Gulya AJ, editor. Surgical Anatomy of Temporal bone and dissection guide. 5th ed. Hamilton, Ontario: BC Decker Inc; 2003. p. 769-96.
2. Ralph AN. Temporal bone surgical dissection manual. Los Angeles: House Ear Institute; 2010. p. 1-94.

Biography:

Dr. Vyshnavi V Final year Post graduate from Department of Otorhinolaryngology Sri Devaraj urs medical college Kolar, Karnataka, India

Point Of Care Ultrasound (POCUS)- An Alternate to Rescue Laryngoscopy in Evaluation of Paediatric Stridor

Dr. Deepa Shivnani ¹, Dr. E V Raman¹

¹ Children's Airway & Swallowing centre (CASC) , Manipal Hospital, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Email: deepa.shivnani14@gmail.com

Abstract:

Paediatric airway evaluation is critical for safe and effective management of airway lesions which present with stridor. The laryngeal lesions may cause symptoms ranging from hoarseness to severe obstruction of the airway. In such lesions, preliminary diagnosis and postoperative surveillance is difficult in paediatric age group. The gold standard modality in stridor evaluation is laryngoscopy examination under anaesthesia and to certain extent, computed tomography imaging, which is time consuming and comes with added risk of anaesthesia and radiation exposure respectively.

The use of Point Of Care Ultrasound(POCUS) has been well established in emergency medicine and in intensive care. Literature demonstrates that POCUS is a safe and validated tool that can be used in emergency care, whilst paediatric specific data is limited. We have demonstrated the use of ultrasound in airway evaluation in children who came to paediatric emergency department with stridor. Our objective was to evaluate the ultrasonographic appearance of laryngeal pathologies in paediatric cases and compare the findings with laryngoscopy. The images and videos were taken during ultrasound and compared with laryngoscopy findings. On Ultrasound examination, appearance of laryngeal pathologies such as respiratory papilloma were easily identifiable as discrete, hyperechoic lesions on the relatively hypoechoic background of the true vocal cords. The dynamic collapsibility of epiglottis was noticed in laryngomalacia cases(video available).

This study establishes Laryngeal ultrasonography as a useful diagnostic tool for operative planning for management of stridor in children with the advantages of simple, highly accurate, non-anaesthetic, no radiation exposure, non-invasive, painless and less expensive than other techniques. It can be helpful for the diagnosis of stridor caused in paediatric age group to avoid laryngoscopy under anaesthesia to a certain extent.

Figure 1: Ultrasound image on the left shows the hyperechoic laryngeal papillomatous lesions which were confirmed with Laryngoscopy findings shown on the right side

Figure 2: Ultrasound image on the left shows the subglottic stenosis which was confirmed with laryngoscopy as shown on the right side

Keyword:

Airway, Laryngoscopy, Laryngomalacia, POCUS, Paediatric Airway, Paediatric Stridor Respiratory Papillomatosis, Subglottic Stenosis

References:

1. O. Adi, K. M. Sum, A. H. Ahmad, M. A. Wahab, L. Neri, and N. Panebianco, "Novel role of focused airway ultrasound in early airway assessment of suspected laryngeal trauma," *Ultrasound J.*, vol. 12, no. 1, p. 37, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1186/s13089-020-00186-3.
2. S. K. Potter and M. J. Griksaitis, "The role of point-of-care ultrasound in paediatric acute respiratory distress syndrome: emerging evidence for its use," *Ann. Transl. Med.*, vol. 7, no. 19, . 507, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.21037/atm.2019.07.76.

Trans-nasal Endoscopic Repair without Stenting in Bilateral Congenital Bony Choanal Atresia: A Step By Step Approach

Dr Deepa Shivnani¹, Dr E V Raman¹

¹ Children's Airway & Swallowing centre (CASC), Manipal Hospital, Bangalore, Karnataka, India

Email: deepa.shivnani14@gmail.com

Abstract:

“Birth without breath” is the precise description of Choanal Atresia (CA). It is a rare disorder but can be life threatening if not diagnosed accurately and on time. There are five different approaches that have been described for surgical treatment of CA: (1) trans-nasal, (2) trans-palatal, (3) trans-antral, (4) trans-septal and (5) sublabial-transnasal. The purpose of this study is to analyze the effectiveness of TRANSNASAL endoscopic repair of bony congenital CA without stenting.

Methods: This case series includes 4 children (aged 6 days - 18 days) who presented or referred to our Hospital with congenital bilateral CA. All patients underwent transnasal endoscopic repair by removing the atretic plate without stenting. A step by step approach with documentation of all images done. All patients were followed up for 18 months.

Results: Two patients were male and two were female. All cases were repaired endoscopically without stenting, only one patient out of 4 patients needed revision surgery. Post operative results were good in terms of restenosis except one case.

Conclusion: Trans-nasal Endoscopic repair of CA without stenting is an effective and safe method of treating CA with a high success rate. It appears to result in superior healing without the need for revision surgery.

Figure 1: Surgical step- After the positioning and draping, the nose is topically decongested with vertically cut neuro-patty soaked in decongestant solution (1 ampoule adrenaline, 30 cc saline with 10 drops of .025% oxymetazoline)

References:

1. El-Ahl MA, El-Anwar MW. Stent less endoscopic trans-nasal repair of bilateral choanal atresia starting with resection of vomer. Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol. 2012;76:1002-6.
2. Gujrathi CS, Daniel SJ, James AL, Forte V. Management of bilateral choanal atresia in the neonate: an institutional review. Int J Pediatr Otorhinolaryngol. 2004; 68(4):399-407.